

In search of superconducting molecules/materials

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Energy crisis, environmental pollution, population explosion, sustainable development etc. are popular public catchwords for the last century. To minimize energy loss is on the other hand improve the sustainability of energy use. Transmission and Distribution (T & D) losses are both technical and management part in the power grid in the process of transporting electricity from generating stations to points of consumption. The loss is reached to ~30% of power generation. It has multiple impact on socio-economic condition. The metallic conductor shows super-conductivity at very low temperature which has techno-management problem. There is an upsurge in the research for exploration of superconducting materials at room temperature and high temperature. The coordination polymer shows tunable electrical properties. Recently, Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs) have received intensive attention in the field of charge storage and transportation. These are exceptional hybrid crystalline porous materials that show powerful room temperature to high temperature superconductivity. This review accounts on the effect of composition, structure, binding etc. of the molecules/materials on the electrical conductivity to superconductivity.

Keywords: Metal organic framework (MOF), superconductivity, coordination polymer.

1. Introduction

The flow of electrons through the molecules or materials refer to electrical conduction or generation of current. The electronic configuration of molecule provides distribution of electrons in valence band (VB) and/or conduction band (CB) those are

closer to Fermi level. When VB overlaps on CB the flow of electron does not need any extra energy and the material is electrical conductor (Fig. 1). If the energy gap is sufficiently large and is not reached by common process then it is called insulator¹. The semiconductor lies in between conductor and insulator and flows electron under forcing condition (temperature, pressure, doping of right materials etc.). The band gap is the energy difference between CB and BV (ΔE) and is greater than 9 eV in insulator and semiconductor have band gap < 3.5 eV. In terms of electrical conductivity the insulators have $\sigma < 10^{-8}$ S cm⁻¹ (diamond : 10^{-14} S cm⁻¹); semiconductors have a conductivity $10^{-8} < \sigma < 10^3$ S cm⁻¹ (Si: range is 10^{-5} S cm⁻¹ to 10^3 S cm⁻¹); the conductors are materials with high conductivities: 10^3 S cm⁻¹ $< \sigma$ (like silver: 10^6 S cm⁻¹)². The charge density is the key factor to propose electrical conductivity of a material; typically, a metallic conductor of charge density $> 10^{20}$ cm³ is of high electrical conductivity (> 100 S cm⁻¹). The electrical conductivity (σ) is expressed as given by eq. 1.

$$\sigma = ne\mu_e + pe\mu_h \quad (1)$$

where n or p is the number density of carriers, their charge (e), and the electron mobility is μ_e and hole mobility is μ_h .

The charge transport barrier between VB and CB is the reason for classification of materials with reference to electrical conductivity³. Upon transportation of electron from VB to CB, a positive hole (h^+) is formed in VB and negative charge (e) in CB. On considering, the electrons and holes as free charge carriers, the charge density is determined by the eq. 2

$$n = n_0 \exp(-E_a/kT) \quad (2)$$

where n_0 = prefactor, k = the Boltzmann constant, and T = absolute temperature, E_a = activation energy.

However, metallic wire electricity distribution process causes $\sim 30\%$ transmission loss due to heating and discharging and there is a dedicated search for organic compounds and

Fig. 1. Schematic idea of conductor, semiconductor, insulator.

hybrid (organic-inorganic) materials those could have almost zero resistance so that superconductivity may be observed.

Fig. 2. A plot of resistance (R) vs Temperature (T , K) for Mercury (Hg).

2. Brief history of discovery of superconductivity⁴⁻¹⁴

Dr. Kamerlingh Onnes and Co-workers found that the resistance in a mercury decreased with decrease in temperature (Fig. 2) and suddenly vanished at 4.2 K (liquid He, first liquefied by Onnes group). He communicated that “*Mercury has passed into a new state, which on account of its extraordinary electrical properties may be called the superconductive state*”. He referred it as “*supraconductivity*” and the term “superconductivity” had entered in Physics. He received the Nobel Prize in 1913 in Physics.

Fig. 3. The Temperature Dependence of the Electrical Resistivity of a Normal Metal. T_c , the superconducting transition temperature.

Dr. Meissner and Dr. Ochsenfeld observed (1933) that a superconductor behaves a strongly diamagnetic metal and is called the *Meissner-Ochsenfeld effect*. This principle is used for the high speed of Japanese Bullet Train (Maglev trains, speed $\sim 600 \text{ km h}^{-1}$). Each of these superconductors has a characteristic superconducting transition temperature (T_c) at which its resistivity drops to zero (Fig. 3). The superconductivity causes diamagnetism which is due to the formation of diamagnetic electron pairs ($S = 0$) (number, ca $10^{20} - 10^{21} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), which then follow of Bose-Einstein condensation (1924) nature at the superconducting transition temperature, T_c . This approach led in 1957 to the BCS

electron-pairing theory (Bardeen-Cooper-Schrieffer theory; Nobel Prize in 1972) of superconductivity¹¹.

Fig. 4. Bednorz & Müller and their compounds, LaBCO and YBCO.

Dr. Bednorz & Dr. Müller in 1986 prepared Lanthanum (Yttrium)-Barium-Copper oxide (LaBCO or YBCO) and characterized HTS (High Temperature Superconductivity), a truly breakthrough in the field of superconductivity (Fig. 4)¹². They worked at the IBM Research Laboratory in Switzerland. This discovery won these two physicists the Nobel Prize in 1987. The worldwide interest, since then, in HTS to all branches of science and engineering especially to the physicists, chemists, materials scientists and engineers. These compounds exhibit superconductivity up to the remarkably high temperature of 164 K.

3. Superconductors: Organic to Inorganic compounds

The field of supercomputer is dominated by organic molecules for more than two decades since 1970. Planar delocalized

p-conjugated orbitals afford advantage to secure conduction columns (Fig. 5). A typical example of organic conductor is TTF (tetrathiafulvalene)-based donors. The replacement of S by Se or mixed S/Se delocalized molecules lead to noncovalent interactions in one-dimensional structures to increase the stability of the electronic array and prevent phase transitions towards lower-conducting structural arrangements and lower the resistance (Fig. 6)¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

Fig. 5. Formation of delocalized p-bonds. The planar organic molecules with p-conjugated orbitals heap up and form a conduction column.

Charge-Transfer salt of organic compounds (Fig. 6) formed by electron donor - electron acceptor molecules as well as polyenes, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons ($T_c = 33$ K at ambient pressure), graphite ($T_c = 15.1$ K at 7.5 GPa), carbon nanotube ($T_c = 15$ K in zeolite), fullerene ($T_c = 38$ K at 0.7 GPa), Single component organic compound ($T_c \leq 2.3$ K at 58 GPa), B doped diamond ($T_c = 10$ K) etc. show superconducti-

vity below T_c and at particular pressure. The hole doped C_{60} intercalated with $CHBr_3$ shows highest T_c (117 K).

Fig. 6. A few interesting Organic Superconductors.

The organic conductors are low dimensional delocalized systems with low thermal stability and undergo easy weathering. Although they are interesting, however, the stability in acidic environment, fatigue after several cycles make them challenging.

Besides very low T_c and high P_c are technologically disappointing. These have entrusted to find out organic-inorganic hybrid superconducting materials. They are scientifically interested in their own rights, but it is also hoped that results and insights gained in studies of these systems will be a useful step towards the comprehension of high T_c superconductors.

Metal-dithiolene and macrocyclic complexes show remarkable conductance which is supported by the overlap of extended ligand orbitals. Superconductivity of coordination complexes were investigated since 1970s¹⁸⁻²⁰. A linear chain stacked compound of tetracyanoplatinate namely Krogmann's salt²¹ described as molecular wires, $K_2[Pt(CN)_4]X_{0,3} \cdot 2,5 H_2O$ ($X = Cl, Br$) exhibit highly anisotropic electrical conductivity reported in 1968 Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Krogman's salt, $K_2[Pt(CN)_4]X_{0,3} \cdot 2,5H_2O$ (Molecular wire).

In 1971 by Chevrel *et al.* reported class of metal cluster, $M_xMo_6S_8$ (M = alkali, alkaline earth, transition metals) who show high temperature superconductivity²²; these are known as Chevrel Phases (Fig. 8). These compounds serve as prominent heterogeneous catalyst²³ for Hydrogen evolution reaction (HER), Oxygen Reduction Reaction (ORR), CO_2 reduction reaction catalysts (CO_2RR) and are potential superconductor.

A common feature of the structure of these clusters is a Mo_6 octahedron consisting of 6 tightly packed Mo atoms (Mo-Mo distances in the range of 2.67 and 2.78 Å). Each face of the octahedron is capped by a sulphur atom forming a S_8 cube around the Mo_6 octahedron, thus there is a Mo_6 octahedron within a S_8 cube (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Encapsulation of Mo_6 (Octahedron) in the cube of bridged S_8 (μ_3 -S) followed by the Cubic Pb^{2+} in the Chevrel Phases.

Perovskites like $SrTiO_3$ (3.2 eV), $LaAlO_3$, Lanthanum (Yttrium)-Barium-Copper oxide (LaBCO or YBCO) show HTS (High Temperature Superconductivity); cubic niobium-containing alloys to layered copper-containing oxides of perovskite-type structure are a truly breakthrough in superconductivity (Fig. 4). Metal complexes of highly conjugated ligands like dithiolene, tetrathiafulvalene, tetraazaannulene, phthalocyanines, glyoximates etc. show very high conductivity (Figs. 9, 10).

Fig. 9. A few molecular structures of macrocyclic metal complexes: metal bis(glyoximate), metal tetraazaanulene, LnBCuO, metal phthalocyanine, metal-thiolene complexes.

Fig. 10. A series of dithiolenes and derivatives and Ni-bis(dithiolene) complexes (the conductivity lies $0.05\text{--}3.3\text{ S cm}^{-1}$ under the highest applied pressures of $10\text{--}11\text{ GPa}$)²⁶.

4. Superconductivity of coordination polymer

The Electrical conductivity of materials is summarized in the edited volumes of Inorganic Materials^{24,25}. The first molecular inorganic superconductor, [TTF] [Ni(dmit)₂]₂ (σ , Superconductivity = 10^5 S cm⁻¹ below 0.8 K under the application of a hydrostatic pressure of 7.7 Kbar) is discovered in 1986 by Patrick Cassoux *et al.* although its metal like conductivity (σ , 300–400 S cm⁻¹) was discovered two years earlier (1984). Since then, many researchers synthesized different coordination complexes and polymers to explore the right material for superconductivity study.

The coordination complexes and coordination polymers (CPs)/Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs) based on the metal bis(dithiolene) moiety are highly conductive^{27,28}, and the covalency of the metal–sulfur bonds in these materials are likely important for through bond charge transport. There are two acceptable charge transportation model (Fig. 11): (a) band transport and (b) hopping transport.

Recently, Metal Organic Frameworks (MOFs) have received intensive attention²⁹ in the field of charge storage and transportation. Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are unique organic-inorganic hybrid crystalline porous materials that consist of a regular array of positively charged metal nodes coordinated by organic ‘linker’. The MOFs have large porosity, high surface area and commonly used for gas absorption and separation, liquid separation and purification, electrochemical energy storage, catalysis, and sensing. In the last few years electrically conductive MOFs are studied because of their applications in electrocatalysis, chemiresistive sensing, and in the design of energy storage technologies.

The mechanism of charge transport in MOFs is difficult to propose unambiguously whether band-like transport or charge hopping transport or combination of both. The structure has great role in the grain boundary resistance in polycrystalline samples. The presence of redox-active metals or linkers, as

well as small spatial separation between these components, can promote charge hopping (through space) along with band transport through bonds (Fig. 12).

Fig. 11. Charge transportation Model: (a) ballistic band-like charge transport and (b) hopping charge transport. Arrow indicates the direction of electron flow from high to low electric potential energy (denoted as E).

In band transport, electrons move along the smooth energy profile, while in hopping transport, movement of electrons is gated by activation energy barrier (E_a). The structure, composition, arrangement, electronic configuration, size, crystallinity etc. are the parameters to monitor the efficiency of charge transportation.

Fig. 12. Electron transport Scheme via (a) a redox hopping mechanism and (b) a guest-promoted pathway involving host-guest interactions.

A 2D lattice, $[\text{Cu}_3(\text{C}_6\text{S}_6)]_n$ (Cu-BHT, BHT = Benzenehexathiol)^{30,31} is geometrically frustrated and allows π -d conjugation which shows unconventional superconductivity; the monolayer Cu-BHT has a critical temperature (T_c) of 4.43 K while T_c of bulk Cu-BHT is 1.58 K. The result is explained based on spin-fluctuations in the 2D lattice (Fig. 13).

Although Cd(II), d^{10} , is not a transition metal and does not have unpaired electron(s) but the complex of bridging fumarate and N-Pyridin-2-yl-N'-pyridin-4-ylmethylene-hydrazine is a 2D Coordination polymer (2D-CP), $\{[\text{Cd}_4(\text{ppmh})_4(\text{fum})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\}_3$

Fig. 13. Cu-BHT Film and conductivity dependence.

Sinha

$H_2O\}n$ (H_2 fum, fumaric acid; ppmh) and shows optical band gap 3.29 eV which implies semiconducting nature (Fig. 13). The plots imply that the conductivity is improved upon light

Fig. 14. 2D Cd-Coordination Polymer and high electrical conductivity.

irradiation (DC conductivity: dark, 0.87×10^{-3} and light, $2.45 \times 10^{-3} \text{ S m}^{-1}$) and approves the Schottky Barrier Diode (SBD) feature³².

Doping of hetero ions/atoms/molecules enhances the electrical conductivity³³. This is observed in case of doping of Cu^{2+} in the cationic coordination polymers (CP) of $[\text{Hg}_2(\text{abpy})_2]_n[\text{PF}_6]_{2n}$ (**1**) (abpy = 2,2'-azobispyridine) which shows high electrical conductivity, 320 S cm^{-1} and on binding with Cu^{2+} the improved conductivity becomes $2.34 \times 10^4 \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ (Fig. 15).

Fig. 15. Hg(I)-azopyridine polymer and its conductivity.

Conclusion

A preliminary future design of Metal Organic Framework as energy storage and transporting material focuses in this appraisal. Metal Organic Frameworks are composed of metal ions as nodes and organic linker with permanent porosity. The electrical conductivity is not only the property of the components of the MOFs but also contributed from their framework structure. Recent development is focused towards the design of superconducting MOFs. Future researchers may select their career in this regard to help sustainable development.

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Sinha

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Prof. Chittaranjan Sinha

Dr. C. Sinha, Professor and Former Head, Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Kolkata is teaching chemistry (especially Inorganic Chemistry) at UG and PG courses and has started research in Burdwan University on metal assisted C-H activation, coupling (C-N, C-O) reactions; coordination chemistry of azoheterocycles with chemical, electrochemical and biochemical activities. Azoimidazole appended polymers are designed for heavy metal purification, separation. Photochromism of arylazoimidazoles and their metal complexes were explored when he joined Jadavpur University. Photoluminescent molecules are used for sensing of ions and molecules at trace level (nM). Functionalisation of sulfonamide antibiotics and their metal complexes are characterized and biomedical applications are studied. His group is engaged on the design of Coordination Polymers/MOFs and their applications in gas absorption, photo-conductivity, ion sensing, catalytic reactions, C-C coupling reactions, magnetic measurements etc. So far, he has published 400+ research articles; 47 students awarded PhD degree; Scopus h-index is 44 and citations 6832. His *teaching* is appreciated by Association of *Chemistry Teachers* awarding the *Best. Chemistry Teacher Award* (2012) and Tata Chemicals. Dr. Sinha has been elected as Fellow of West Bengal Academy of Science & Technology (2018). Dr. C. Sinha has been included in the Stanford University's list of the top 2% scientists in the world out of 2049 scientists from India in 2021.